

To cool or not to cool? That was the question.

Drinking in Spain in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries

Introduction

From antiquity to the Renaissance, in the Greek-Latin and Arabic traditions, no medicine treatise does not contain multiple references to water consumption. Medical texts devote much of their dietary sections to examining the liquid element types, origin, varieties, how to obtain it, the conditions it has to have to be drinkable, and the procedures for purifying it. Later, the subject of culinary water, its quality, the recommended drinking habits, its benefits, and its dangers, was widely discussed in continental Europe and Britain in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries.

A somewhat different and focused attitude, which substantially is the core of this paper, arises from works written in the Iberian Peninsula. Nevertheless, by the late Renaissance, Iberia seems to have been the only region in which the medical debate centered on the convenience, or the dangers of drinking water and other beverages cooled by ice or snow. Historically, the art of refrigeration based on natural ice and snow is very old and was practiced long before any other method was used by almost all ancient civilizations.¹ However, the uniquely obsessive interest in the benefits and dangers of cooling drinks is shown by the disproportionate attention dedicated to it in Spanish medical texts from the beginning of the sixteenth to the eighteenth century.²

¹ For a comprehensive account of the historical development of the preference for cooled water in Antiquity and the Early Middle Ages, see: Fernando Beltrán Cortés, *Apuntes para una Historia Del Frío en España*, Madrid: Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas - Dpto. de Publicaciones, 1983, pp. 51-70.

² For a comprehensive list of Spanish medical literature from Roman times up to 1801, see: Joaquín de Villalba y Guitarte, *Epidemiología española o Historia cronológica de las pestes, contagios, epidemias y epizootias que han acaecido en España desde la venida de las cartagineses hasta el año 1801: Con noticia de algunas otras enfermedades de esta especie que han sufrido los españoles en otros reinos, y de los autores nacionales que han escrito sobre esta materia*, Madrid: Imprenta de Fermín Villalpando, 1803. For a corpus of Spanish Medical Texts, which includes 55 medical manuscripts and early printed books on the whole field of medicine, see the website of the Hispanic Seminary of Medieval Studies (HSMS): <http://www.hispanicseminary.org/t&c/med/index-en.htm>. For a comprehensive description of the subjects and commentaries of Spanish medical

For several thousand years, man has considered snow as a highly therapeutic product when it comes to regulating the organic balance of the human body and, since then, its collection and storage have been a constant in many towns and cultures.

In Spain, the custom of drinking cooled beverages was almost unknown in the sixteenth century, but by the seventeenth, it became sort of a fashion to drink water cooled with snow. The growth of this practice brought about heated discussions amongst medical doctors, one party favoring the use of snow, the other against it. The result was prolific literature on this subject, sometimes including personal overtones, as we can appreciate in the titles of several of these books.³

1) Water consumption in Spain

The copious medical literature in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries considers liquids as both food and medicine, and the consumption of water was among the factors that influence health.⁴ A pediatric text from 1604 declares: "Even if water does not nourish, it is useful as medicine."⁵

Understandably, as in other geographical areas, most of the population collected water directly from rivers, with all the risks involved – all the urban detritus were thrown into the rivers as well. Good water used to be in the hands of a minority of privileged people, so it also served to distinguish social classes. And if

literature up to 1840, see Anastasio Chinchilla, *Anales históricos de la medicina en general, y biográfico-bibliográfico de la española en particular*, (7 volumes), Valencia: Imp. de D. José Mateu Cervera, 1841-1846.

³ Natalia Juan García, "Prácticas alimentarias en los siglos XVII y XVIII en el clero regular de Aragón – los manjares de la comunidad de monjes de San Juan de la Peña," *Studium: Revista de Humanidades*, No. 15, (2009), pp. 165-198, refers to this curious and heated debate, giving a detailed bibliography, in footnote No. 49, pp. 191-192.

⁴ For a detailed article on this subject see: Andrea María Bau y Gabriela Fernanda Canavese, "'Agua que cura, agua que alimenta'. La dietética para sanos y el uso del agua en la sociedad española bajomedieval y moderna," *Cuadernos de historia de España*, Vol. 80, (2006), pp. 127-146 and Andrea María Bau y Gabriela Fernanda Canavese, "El uso del agua como terapia medicinal en la dietética hispánica bajomedieval y moderna," *Fundación*, (2010) pp. 158-164.

⁵ ["Y aunque el agua no aproveche por alimento, a lo menos les será útil por medicamento,"] in Cristóbal Pérez de Herrera, *Texto y Concordancias de la Defensa de las criaturas de tierna edad*, Valladolid: Luis Sánchez, 1604, original in Biblioteca nacional de Madrid, edited by Andrea María Bau, New York: Hispanic Seminary of Medieval Studies, 2004, fols. 44v-45r, extracted from the Website of the Hispanic Seminary of Medieval Studies (HSMS), <http://www.hispanicseminary.org/t&c/med/dct/framconc.htm>, accessed 13 August 2012.

the characteristics of the water consumed distinguished the rich from the poor, they were no less different in the way they were drunk, especially in the summer and at latitudes such as southern Spanish, and, in general, in Mediterranean Europe. Good water, but above all cold, was not available to everyone and very soon became a symbol of social status.

By the last decades of the sixteenth century and the beginning of the seventeenth, we see the appearance of the "Literature of cold drinking," which will last to our present days.⁶ Overall, the controversy around the drinking of cold water in Spain during the 16th and 17th centuries appears in a wide range of medical, literary, and religious texts. It concerned the benefits or detriments of drinking refrigerated water, which could allegedly lead to death when consumed in excess. In addition to the 'scientific' reasons favorable and contrary to the consumption of cold water, disparate arguments fed a widespread medical debate, which peaked between 1555 and 1576. Numerous works are published in all major cities in Spain, and some in America, which review different ways that were traditionally used to cool drinks and can be summarized in the following: with snow, in the open air, in wells, in cellars or caves, with air, and with nitro and saltpeter.

Already in the early Middle Ages were published some treatises where the proper use of snow is discussed, such as the "*Liber Peregrinationis*," a guide for the *Camino de Santiago* from the 12th century, which advised pilgrims not to consume fish that was not obtained directly from the rivers, due to the lack of snow deposits to provide it as a preservative. Some cookery books were also published, such as "Accounts of the Royal Household of Pedro II de Aragón" [*Cuentas de la Casa Real de Pedro II de Aragón*], which collects notes on the making and consumption of ice cream.⁷

⁶ Luis de Toro, *Discursos o consideraciones sobre la materia de enfriar la bebida en que se trata de las diferencias de enfriar y del uso y propiedad de cada una*: año del Señor 1569. Reprinted in Salamanca: Universidad de Salamanca, 1991, p. 13.

⁷ Ginés Rosa Lopez, *Los pozos de nieve de Sierra Espuña (el comercio de la nieve en el Reino de Murcia, siglos XVI-XX)*, Murcia: Mancomunidad Turística de Sierra de Espuña, 2002, extracted from María Asunción Romero Díaz, Francisco Belmonte Serrato, "Los pozos de nieve de Sierra Espuña (Murcia): aspectos históricos, culturales, geográficos y climáticos que propiciaron el desarrollo de la industria artesanal del hielo," in Concepción de la Peña Velasco (ed.), *En torno al Barroco: miradas múltiples*, Murcia: Editum, 2006, pp. 113-128.

In 1524, the humanist Juan Luis Vives warned, at times, about the cold: "Keep the body carefully away from the cold and especially the neck, where it does great harm to health and understanding." However, at other times, he recommends it: "Don't drink after dinner; or if the need forces you, be it a small quantity, but fresh."⁸

Along similar lines, a well-known physician of the fifteenth century, Hernán Alfonso de Chirino, discouraged cold drinks completely, neither when waking up nor before meals, and even after eating until digestion is made. The only exception he allows was when suffering from heartburn or when too much wine was drunk the day before. In any case, he also prescribes that the amount consumed should not be plentiful.⁹

Opinions on the value of water as a remedy were widely opposed: very cold water was either considered wonderful for all kinds of maladies or a threat to the health of elderly, unfit people. As a rule, a medieval tradition was not in favor of the consumption of beverages cooled by snow; if drunk, it was advised to do it in small gulps, a recommendation still popular at present. Too cold water was blamed for impairing digestion and cooling the blood. It was usual at the time to write books instructing medical nurses (who were almost exclusively male) on different cures, and in this framework, drinking water was frequently referred to as an important factor, either for the treatment of specific illnesses or in general. One of such books – *Instructions for nurses on how to administer remedies for all kinds of illnesses...*, recommends reminding the patient to drink water, even if he doesn't feel thirsty, especially when having a high fever, and advises that drinking hot water is appropriate.¹⁰ Water to be drunk at the table should be cold but not cooled neither

⁸ Juan Luis Vives, "Introducción a la sabiduría," *Obras completas* (2 volumes), Vol. 1, Madrid: M. Aguilar, 1947, pp. 1213-1214, (original published in Valencia in 1524). For a philosophical discussion on the nature ('temperamento,' sic.) of snow, see Isidro Pérez Merino, *Breve antiapología al discurso nuevo del doctor Miguel Fernández de la Peña: método verdadero del uso del agua de nieve en día de purga*, Jaén: Francisco Perez de Castilla, 1641, pp. 2-5).

⁹ Hernán Alfonso de Chirino, *Menor daño de la medicina*, Toledo: Joan de Villaquiran, 1513, cap. XVIII y Luis Lobera de Ávila, *Libro del regimiento de la salud, y de la esterilidad de los hombres y mugeres, y d[e] las e[n]fermedades d[e] los niños, y otras cosas utilissimas*, Valladolid: Sebastian Martinez, 1551, cap. VII.

¹⁰ Isidoro de la Pastora y Nieto, *Una verdad histórica relativa al uso del agua por los médicos españoles en el tratamiento de las enfermedades: Discurso que en el acto de recibir la solemne investidura de doctor en Medicina y Cirugía pronunció ante el claustro de la Universidad Central Central de Madrid, Facultad de Medicina*, Madrid: Imprenta de Díaz y Compañía, 1834, p. 12.

by snow nor by recently melted snow since the intake of the most frigid drink can damage the organism because it suddenly alters the harmony of human nature.¹¹ Along similar lines, a well-known physician of the fifteenth century, Hernán Alfonso de Chirino, discouraged cold drinks completely, neither when waking up nor before meals, and even after eating until digestion is made. The only exception he allows was when suffering from heartburn or when too much wine was drunk the day before. In any case, he also prescribes that the amount consumed should not be plentiful.¹²

Renewed testimonies about this subject resurface by the middle of the sixteenth century. Pedro Mejía, a Sevillian humanist and historian, wrote about the recent fashion of "cold drinking" among the upper classes in his work *Coloquios y diálogos* (1547). In one of the dialogs, we witness a discussion on whether cold drinks are beneficial or damaging to health:

Why, Mr. Master, is it a sin to drink cold? (Teacher) No sir, it is licit and tasty and a natural thing, because thirst (as Aristotle says) is an appetite for the humid and cold, as hunger is for the dry and hot, and that is why we naturally want cold beverages and hot delicacies. Fruits are eaten to moisten and temper the heat: so that cold drinking is not bad, but extremes are never good...¹³

2. Sickness and death from drinking cold water. A real danger?

By 1555, the physician and humanist Andrés Laguna Segovia, was not in favor of prescribing cold potions: "Do not drink cold wines with ice, or with snow, because they notably destroy teeth, suffocate natural heat, make your chest and stomach raw."¹⁴ Doctors who line up on the anti-cold drink side had their first standard-bearer in Andrés Laguna. The Segovian doctor explains how the qualities of cooled

¹¹ Luis Lobera de Ávila, *Vanquete de Nobles Cavalleros*, en José María López Piñero, *El Vanquete de Nobles Cavalleros (1530) de Luis Lobera de Ávila y la higiene individual del siglo XVI*, Madrid: Ministerio de Sanidad y Consumo, 1991, p. 30.

¹² De Chirino, *Menor daño de la medicina*, cap. XVIII y Lobera de Ávila, *Libro del regimiento de la salud*, cap. VII.

¹³ Pedro Mejía and Margaret Lois Mulroney, *Diálogos o coloquios of Pedro Mejía*, Iowa City: State University of Iowa, 1930, pp. 76-77. For the original version, see: Pedro Mejía, *Diálogos o coloquios de magnífico caballero Pedro Mejía*, Sevilla: por Cristobal Alvarez, 1551.

¹⁴ Andrés de Laguna, *Pedacio Dioscórides Anazarbeo, acerca de la materia medicinal y de los venenos mortíferos, traduzido de lengua Griega, en la vulgar Castellana e ilustrado con claras y substanciales annotationes*, Amberes: Juan Latio; 1555, p. 511.

water are not the same as water in its natural state and have dire health consequences:

The melting water of hail, snow, and ice is more than pestilential, because when all these things were frozen, their lighter parts dissipate, so that only the thick ones remain, which inside the body will cause infinite diseases.¹⁵

Cristóbal de Vega, professor in Alcalá and court physician, in his monumental *Liber de Arte Medendi* (1564), gives an almost identical explanation vilifying artificially cooled water. De Vega recruits arguments from the field of ethics, referring to this fashion as a regrettable plague, which he condemns:

I regret the misfortune of our time because I see that this Epicurean plague has devastated first the Germans, then the Flemings and the Gauls and now the old restraint of the Spaniards is also buried.¹⁶

Other doctors denounce the lack of sobriety and temperance, and the gluttony that shows the desire to drink water and any other cold drink (references to wine usually go hand in hand).¹⁷ The native of Plasencia, Doctor Luis de Toro, a student of Vega at the University of Salamanca and author of an unpublished pamphlet in 1569 about the cooling of drinks, is paradigmatic of this way of thinking. He could not be more explicit in its prologue:

Before writing this I openly understood how difficult a business would be undertaking to predicate sobriety and temperance on cold drinking, especially at this time when this vice has grown so much and produced such deep roots that it is almost considered a virtuous custom and a pledge of nobility and cavalry.¹⁸

¹⁵ De Laguna, *Pedacio Dioscórides Anazarbeo*, p. 513.

¹⁶ Christophori a Vega, *Liber de arte medendi: cum indice locupletissimo*, Ludguni: apud Gulielmum Rovillium, 1564. Extracted from the translation of Nelia Rosa Vellisca Gutiérrez, *Cristóbal de Vega. Sobre el arte de curar, Traducción anotada del libro II De arte medendi*. (El cuidado de la salud en la España del siglo XVI), Valladolid: Ediciones Universidad de Valladolid; 2018, p. 102.

¹⁷ For an excellent analysis of the different factors affecting this controversy, especially its ethical aspects, see Martín Ferreira, Ana Isabel and Cristina de la Rosa Cubo, "La polémica médica en torno al consumo de agua fría en la España Moderna." *Dynamis: Acta Hispanica ad Medicinæ Scientiarumque Historiam Illustrandam*, 2018, Vol. 38, Núm. 2, pp. 407-426.

¹⁸ Quote by Justo Pedro Hernández González, *La literatura médica sobre el beber frío en la Europa del siglo XVI. Una polémica renacentista*, Vigo: Academia del Hispanismo; 2009, pp. 35-36.

Some authors in the sixteenth century not only refer to the intake of cold water pointing to the dangers to health, arising from excesses, but see it as a direct cause of the death of illustrious young characters, who got pleasure from a dissolute life, such as the Dolphin of France and Philip the Beautiful. A profile of the candidate to die in such a way is set – young people of athletic appearance, without known diseases, who play or exercise under the summer sun, who feel thirsty, who sweat, fatigued and drink (water or wine) very cold, after which they suddenly die.¹⁹

The most complete work on the subject was written in 1576 by Francesc Micó (1528-1592), a Catalan doctor, a native of Vic – *Relief of thirst, where it is discussed the need we have to cool and refresh our beverages with snow, the conditions required doing so, and which bodies can tolerate it.*²⁰ Micó described thirst as a physiological need and cited testimonies from ancient philosophers and physicians, who considered it beneficial to have beverages cooled or at least refreshed. His main conclusion was that if cooled drinks are recommended for feverish sick people, they surely should be good for healthy people.²¹

Alonso Díez Daza, a physician from Seville, wrote in 1576 a small volume, entitled *The book of the benefits and damages that are caused by drinking exclusively water, how to choose the best and correct the one which is not, and how it should be drunk in warm times without causing damage.*²² He dedicated the second chapter to explaining how to recognize 'good water'. His advice is just plain common sense: "... [water] has to have good taste, good color, good odor, as Galen stated..."²³ In a curious discussion he grades the quality of river water according to the direction of the flow: "...best from rivers flowing from west to east, second best when flowing from east to west, worst when flowing north to south or

¹⁹ Ferreira, "La polémica médica," p. 420.

²⁰ Francesc Micó, *Alivio de los sedientos: en el qual se trata la necesidad que tenemos de beber frío y refrescado con nieve, y las condiciones que para esto son menester, y quales cuerpos lo pueden libremente soportar*, Barcelona: Matheo Barceló, 1792 (originally published in Barcelona by Diego Galán, 1576.)

²¹ Micó, *Alivio de los sedientos*, pp. 35-36.

²² Alonso Díez Daza (or Daça), *Libro de los provechos y daños que provienen con la sola bebida del agua; cómo se ha de escoger la mejor y rectificar la que no es tal, y cómo se ha de beber fría en tiempo de calor sin que haga daño*, (2 volumes), Vol. 1, Sevilla: Alonso de la Barrera, 1576.

²³ *Ibid.*, fol. 13 v.

south to north.”²⁴ Not surprisingly, and although cautioning that “not because it is his ‘homeland and own nation’... Seville’s water is excellent, as its river flows to the east.”²⁵ The eighth chapter of the book is dedicated to recommended modes of water consumption. His advice, which he bases on Hippocrates, is once again logical: “...drink moderately – as the body regulates hunger, so it does with thirst...”²⁶ Throughout the entire volume, the same author extensively notes the danger of drinking cold water, as he had seen people die instantly while doing so. Certain conditions had to be met to make cold drinking acceptable, such as being young, doing it in summer, and having healthy intestines.

The historian Francisco Bermúdez de Pedraza (1608) extols the Genil River (which flows through Granada into the Guadalquivir River) because of the coldness of its waters, “...snow water that melts away.”²⁷ He praised the custom of the Grenadines to dispense cold drinks: “... that many will stop eating first than drinking cold; which is great excellence of Granada, where the snow is so cheap, that there is no poor person who is not rich to spend it ...”²⁸ However, not every melted snow by itself was considered unhealthy, as Mafias Porrás warns in a 1621 manuscript, published in Perú.²⁹

In 1616 the Sevillian doctor Muñoz de Castro glossed in a book dedicated to the subject of the drinks cooled with snow, and the Cordoban doctor Jiménez de Carmona, who practiced in Salamanca, wrote: “of the good use of dripping with

²⁴ Ibid., fol. 15 v.– fol. 18 v.

²⁵ Ibid., fol. 19 r.

²⁶ Ibid., fol. 57 v. – fol. 58 r., 65 v.

²⁷ Francisco Bermúdez De Pedraza: *Antigüedad y excelencias de Granada*, Madrid: Luis Sánchez, 1608, Libro Primero: Descripción de Granada, capítulo séptimo: Del río Genil: “Este río, aunque primero es manso y pequeño hacia el Norte, después a poco trecho, se hace caudaloso y grande, con el agua de nieve que se deshace, y arroyos de fuentes manantiales que se le juntan [...]: el agua se hace tan buena y fría que es la mejor que se bebe.”

²⁸ Idem, idem, second chapter (last paragraph).

²⁹ Matías Porrás, *Breves advertencias para beber frío con nieve*, Lima: Gerónimo de Contreras, 1621. Extracted from Juan García, “Prácticas alimentarias en los siglos XVII y XVIII,” p. 191. Juan García refers to this curious and heated debate, giving a detailed bibliography, in footnote No. 49, pp. 191-192. For an opposite view on the benefits of the utilization of water as a remedy and for almost any kind of treatment involving water, see: Isidro de la Pastora y Nieto, *Una verdad histórica relativa al uso del agua por los médicos españoles en el tratamiento de las enfermedades: Discurso que en el acto de recibir la solemne investidura de doctor en Medicina y Cirugía pronunció ante el claustro de la Universidad Central de Madrid, Facultad de Medicina*, Madrid: Imprenta de Díaz y Compañía, 1834.

snow."³⁰

The Sevillian doctor Juan de Carvajal, author of the book *Utilities of snow*, begins this work thus: "I was moved to write this, seeing that some doctors abhor the use of snow." In his treatise he defends, above all, substituting bloodletting – applied then widely – with the use of snow: "Snow is a medicine by nature and there is no reason to hate it." He continues by enumerating a ridiculously long list of maladies that snow can cure.³¹

One exception to the obsession with the role played by cooled water is another popular book published in 1625, which offers instructions for nurses when physicians are not readily available. It gives a detailed description of when and how water should be administered to sick people, but no mention is made about cold drinks as medicine, or in fact, at all.³²

Another prestigious doctor, Fernando Cardoso, philosopher, and poet, warns, in 1637, that one should drink snow water wisely.³³

The positive effects of cold water drinking on the cure of constipation are widely referred to by Dr. Alonso de Burgos in 1640, in a book intended to refute the position of other physicians from Cordoba, his natal city, who were decidedly against this treatment. Burgos provides detailed instructions on what concerns the recommended water and snow quality and the correct method of dispensing it.³⁴

³⁰ Jerónimo Muñoz de Castro, *Tratado de la nieve, de su generación y propiedades, del mejor uso de ella conveniente a la salud*, Sevilla: Colombina, 1616; Francisco Ximénez de Carmona, *Tratado breve de la Grande Excelencia del Agua, y de sus maravillosas virtudes, calidad, elección, y del buen uso de esfriar con nieve: Que sea nieve, y de sus grandes efectos, cuán necesaria sea para conservar la salud. Que modos hay de esfriar; qual sea el mejor, más saludable, y provechoso*, Sevilla: Alfonso Rodriguez Gamarra, 1616.

³¹ Juan Carvajal, *Utilidades de la nieve: deducidas de la buena medicina*, Sevilla: Simón Faxardo, 1622.

³² Hermano Andrés Fernández (de la Congregación de Bernardino de Obregón), *Instrucción de enfermeros para aplicar los remedios a todo género de enfermedades y acudir a muchos accidentes que sobrevienen en ausencia de los médicos*, Madrid: Imprenta Real, 1625, pp. 132-140.

³³ Fernando de Cardoso, *Utilidades del agua y de la nieve, del beber frío y caliente*, Madrid: Viuda de Alonso Martín, 1637.

³⁴ Alonso de Burgos, *Método curativo y uso de la nieve, en que se declara y prueba la obligación que tienen los médicos de dar a los purgados agua de nieve con las condiciones y requisitos que se dirá*, Córdoba: Andrés Carrillo, 1640, mentioned in: Antonio Hernández Morejón, *Historia bibliográfica de la medicina española*, Volume 5, Madrid: Imprenta de la viuda de Jordan e hijos, 1847, pp. 284-285.

A heated written debate took place in the 1650s on what concerns the character of snow, motivating an exchange that generated several books on the subject, which would eventually dissipate.³⁵ In 1661, Gerónimo Pardo, a doctor from Valladolid and professor of Method at its Royal University, recalled, once again, the danger of sipping directly melted snow.³⁶

Spanish theorists also worry about the time of the day when water is ingested. The positions widely differ among writers. In general, they advise abstaining from drinking water on an empty stomach, although, Simón López, who was considered a famous surgeon and nursing expert, notes in his manual: *Guidelines for nurses and volunteers for the caring of body illnesses* (1668) that hot water is useful in creating a void and relieving stomach superfluities.³⁷ He accepts as valid the custom of drinking cold water, natural or artificially cooled with snow, and drinking during meals. He acknowledges that two or three small gulps after the meal are beneficial for good digestion and "... does not let *fumes* rise to the brain." As for temperature, he considers that water that is not cold can cause nausea, swell the belly, destroy the appetite, and can cause vomiting, colds, and spitting blood. The

³⁵ As examples of this controversy, see Tomás de Murillo y Velarde Jurado, *Responsiva apología, a un tratado del licenciado Don Cristóbal Mirez Carvajal, médico, en que se pretende probar que la nieve es seca a predominio: y aprobación y confirmación de un papel que defiende la opinión contraria ...*, Córdoba: Andres Carrillo, 1650.; Cristóbal Mirez de Carvajal, *Tratado de las cualidades que la nieve tiene a predominio y respuesta a un papel que quiere defender la opinión contraria*, Málaga: Serrano de Vargas y Vreña, 1650; Cristóbal Mirez de Carvajal, *Antología breve en que se prueba el verdadero temperamento que la nieve posee a predominio y de passo se responde a dos apologías que pretenden probar*, Granada: Imprenta Real, por Baltasar de Bolibar, 1652 and Tomás de Murillo y Velarde Jurado, *Resolución filosófica y médica muy útil para médicos y filósofos del verdadero temperamento frío y húmedo de la nieve, en que se trata de sus utilidades y daños y se responde a un tratado que la nieve tiene sequedad a predominio*, Madrid: Julián de Paredes, 1667.

³⁶ Gerónimo Pardo, *Tratado del vino aguado y agua envinada, sobre el aforismo 56 de la sección 7 de Hipocrates*, Valladolid: en la imprenta de Valdivielso, 1661. Quoted by Mariano Alcocer Martínez, *Catálogo Razonado de Obras Impresas en Valladolid 1481-1800*, Valladolid: Junta de Castilla y León, Valladolid, 1993.

³⁷ Simón López, *Directorio de enfermeros y artífice de obras de caridad para curar las enfermedades del cuerpo*. Estudio, transcripción e índices a cargo de Antonio C. García Martínez y Manuel J. García Martínez, Consejo General de Enfermería, Madrid: Enfermundi, 2001. Original: Simón López, *Directorio de enfermeros y artífice de obras de caridad para curar las enfermedades del cuerpo*, Manuscrito Ms. 259, Biblioteca Universitaria de Salamanca, 1668, Capítulo 141. López book is analyzed in Manuel Jesús García Martínez and Antonio Claret García Martínez, "La enseñanza de la enfermería en la España del siglo XVII, el manual de enfermería de Simón López (1668)," *Cultura de los cuidados: Revista de enfermería y humanidades*, No. 3, 1998, pp. 15-23.

drink must be cold, in its proper measure, to promote the restoration of liquids lost in our bodies and to preserve the humidity that prevails in them.³⁸

A religious factor loomed in the background of the controversy. The desire to consume cold water, as exposed by the doctor Luis de Toro already in 1569, never ceased to be considered a sin of gluttony and vanity; it is more, a century later, in the middle of the Spanish Baroque, during the seventeenth century, it is taken a step beyond the hand of religion, and this kind of "cult of the body", which adds to the physical exercise the pleasure of the icy drink, is seen as a mortal sin. It is a vice capable of making the deceased suffer the punishments of Purgatory and, therefore, depriving him of a better outer and eternal life.³⁹

Thus, a contention was imposed in the face of sin. And, if it may be, the sacrifice, as illustrated by the mortifications to which the Aragonese Franciscan Pedro SELLERAS LÁZARO (1555-1622) voluntarily submitted, then told in his an example of uplifting life. Among the anecdotes published on this holy preacher is the deprivation of drinking cold water that imposed itself, even when fatigued and thirsty, so as not to get used to the good.⁴⁰

The great writers of the Golden Century (*Siglo de Oro*) commended cold beverages. Francisco de Quevedo favored cold drinking, thus saying: "I like to drink cold from the snow."⁴¹ In several of his works Cervantes praised cold water: "...and she served instead of water, pure and extremely cold;"⁴² reiterating in the *Quijote* the examples of cooling using snow and of ice wells.⁴³ In yet another work he explains: "The sun heat causes thirst, which has to be quenched with water-

³⁸ *Idem*.

³⁹ Ferreira, "La polémica médica," p. 423.

⁴⁰ *Idem*., p. 424.

⁴¹ "Ostentan aposento con brasero bien proveído en invierno y su agua fresca en verano," in Francisco Gómes de Quevedo Villegas, *Obras satíricas y festivas*, Madrid: Librería de la viuda de Hernando y Company, 1893.

⁴² Miguel de Cervantes Saavedra, *Trabajos de Persiles y Sigismunda*, Madrid: Librería de San Martín, 1859, p. 25.

⁴³ Miguel de Cervantes Saavedra, *El Ingenioso Hidalgo Don Quijote de la Mancha*, Segunda Parte (1615), Capítulo cincuenta y uno: «[...] finalmente, él me va matando de hambre, y yo me voy muriendo de despecho, pues pensé venir a este gobierno a comer caliente y a beber frío.» and in *ídem, ídem, ídem*, Capítulo Cincuenta y ocho: «Digo esto, Sancho, porque bien has visto el regalo, la abundancia que en este castillo que dejamos hemos tenido: pues en mitad de aquellos banquetes sazonados y de aquellas bebidas de nieve.

cooled by snow, by burying water bottles in snow and gently shaking them.”⁴⁴

3) Other beverages, foods, and the *aloja* business

The answer to the question of what was drunk in the Golden Age in Madrid is simple – something like what we drink nowadays. In the 16th century, water and wine were drunk, as much or more than now. What did not seem as successful in Spain as nowadays was beer, even though King Charles V, who arrived from Flanders, made all kinds of efforts to introduce it to the peninsula by bringing from Germany the best brewers of the moment. It was common as well to consume cold drinks such as lemonade and *horchata de chufas*, barley water or oatmeal, and something very fashionable in present times, almond milk.⁴⁵ A special mention should be made of the *aloja* (aloxa), which was drunk in huge quantities in Madrid in summer. It consisted of a blend of water, honey, and spices – such as white pepper or cinnamon, sometimes mixed with wine, to cheat on legal taxation.⁴⁶ It was sold in the Royal Palace during the regency of Doña Mariana of Austria, in the lodges of the comedial pens, in the bullrings, or at the festivals of many cities. The *aloja* was drunk accompanied by waffles, wafers, and a kind of fritters or *churros*. In the capital, there were so many *alojerías* that it was said that, in one of every three portals, *aloja* was sold.

There were curious medical debates about the advantages and disadvantages of cooling foods. Snow was not only used to refrigerate drinks, since among the Spaniards of this time cold fruits were a very appetizing delicacy, as the doctor of Játiva and professor of Seville Francisco Franco tells us:

⁴⁴ Miguel de Cervantes Saavedra, *Obras escogidas de Miguel de Cervantes: Ingenioso hidalgo don Quijote de la Mancha*, Madrid: En la Librería hispano-francesa de Bossange Padre, 1826. Notes to chapter XLV, pp. 356-357. For a description of the most popular travel bottles shape, see: Carmen Abad-Zardoya, “Por Tierra y Mar. El Ajuar de Camino Como Proyección del Espacio Doméstico,” *Res Mobilis Revista internacional de investigación en mobiliario y objetos decorativos*, Vol. 1, No. 1, 2012.

⁴⁵ The horchata de chufa is a refreshing drink (also consumed as a dessert), prepared with water, sugar, and wet (or ground) tiger nuts, in addition to ingredients that enhance its flavors, such as cinnamon and the skin of a lemon.

⁴⁶ Sebastián de Covarrubias Orozco, *Tesoro de la Lengua Castellana o Española*, Madrid: Imprenta Luís Sánchez, 1611, p. 58; Francisco Romero, *Almagro y el Corral de Comedias*, Almagro: Baobab Ediciones, 2003, p. 13.

What will we say about fruits? There is no doubt that the fruit, in principle, as a dessert, is best eaten cold, mainly put on the snow. With how different tastes are eaten cold or hot, with the same difference, you can eat albérchiga or pear, although from the albérchiga it is not very clear if it is a fruit of dessert or first dish. These fruits, put on snow, are eaten with great pleasure, and even who is partly where there is a lack of some fruit, or because they are finished or brought from other places, it will be very good advice to put the fruit in the cellar where the snow was because in that way rot is prevented for some days...⁴⁷

Franco adds a convincing argument: "There is no worse tasting taste than eating a hot melon, nor greater comfort than eating it when it is very cold..."⁴⁸ Francisco Franco was a Sevillian physician and friend of the writer Pedro Mejía. It is no coincidence that almost all the doctors involved in this controversy write and publish their works in the south of Spain, most of them in the populous, and no less hot, city of Seville, which leads us to better understand why the reasons set out by this author in the work we cite.

Of the same opinion is another native of the city, Nicolás Monardes, in whose brief treaty he also uses practical reasons justifying the use and enjoyment of cold water, many of which he shares almost to the letter with Franco, which suggests a prior reading of his text. These can be synthesized into three: the first, which "is used today worldwide;" the second that in Seville is a necessity for its weather; the third that brings health, taste, and content in the face of ills, diseases, and sadness. It is, in short, a question relating to happiness. Supporter of cold eating was once again Monardes: "... because the warmth weakens the stomach, makes the delicacy disappear, begets breezes and causes pain and sorrow"⁴⁹

A huge problem arose for cooling beverages in 1610, when, by government regulation, it was forbidden in Madrid to cool *aloja* with snow.⁵⁰ The following year

⁴⁷ Francisco Franco, *Tratado de lo Nieve*, Madrid: Gonzalo Santonja, 1984 (originally published in 1569), p. 66.

⁴⁸ *Idem.*, p. 75.

⁴⁹ Nicolás de Monardes, *Libro que trata de la nieve, y de sus propiedades, y del modo que se ha de tener, en el beber enfriado con ella, y de los otros modos que hay de enfriar*, Sevilla: Alonso Escrivano; 1574, several remarks throughout pp. 198-206.

⁵⁰ Miguel Herrero García, *La vida española del siglo XVII*, Capítulo I: Las bebidas (1933).

(1611) this order was revoked thanks to a medical report submitted by the *alojeros*.⁵¹

In 1619, according to Herrero-García, the custom of cooling wine for retail sales began in the pantries of the gentlemen entitled to a franchise on food taxes, who abused their privilege by making fraudulent competition to merchants and the public treasury. In that year, the first complaints that wine sold in Madrid came diluted with snow were heard.⁵²

During Felipe IV's reign, in 1625, the Sevillian Santiago Valverde Turices published a book glossing on the medicinal properties of the *aloja*: "The *aloja*, as a summer refreshment, is as beneficial as chocolate in winter."⁵³ This position was not consensual, as we can appreciate in a popular cynical saying in a short theater piece: *Entremés de las Noches de Carnestolendas* – "The *aloja* has killed even more Christians than the doctors."⁵⁴

The Toledan Matias de Porrás was a determined militant of the refrigeration enthusiasts, alluding, for example, that cinnamon water cooled with snow had salutary effects: "It is very true that cinnamon water, strictly speaking, is the best of all those used in medicine, because its heat is moderate, and it does not pass to the liver, ... comforts the stomach..." Porrás only noted two drawbacks in cooling drinks; one, when the agent of cooling is air, and the other, using melted ice/snow water. The authorities agreed with Porrás, and in 1639, they categorically forbade the pouring of ice into the vessels containing drinks.⁵⁵

⁵¹ Beltrán Cortés, *Apuntes para una Historia Del Frío*, p. 197, quoting from *Libro de Alcaldes de Casa y Corte* (1611): "Informe de los doctores Andres Perez (conocido como doctor Guerra, Francisco López y Manuel de Avios, donde ponderan los salutíferos efectos de beber frió con nieve recordando que gracias a esta costumbre "desaparecieron las fiebres tercianas en Valencia y Extremadura."

⁵² "Juan Lozano en nombre de los taberneros de esta corte (...) pido y suplico se les dé licencia para que puedan vender su vino con nieve." Quoted from *Libro de Alcaldes de Casa y Corte* (1619) by Miguel Herrero García, *La vida española del siglo XVII*, Madrid: Gráfica Universal, 1933, Capítulo I: "Las bebidas."

⁵³ "La *aloja*, como refresco de verano, es tan beneficiosa como el chocolate en invierno", in Santiago Valverde Turices, *De la aloja y de su uso*, Sevilla: por Juan de Carrera, 1625, praises the beverage (quoted by Herrero García, *La vida española*, p. 138).

⁵⁴ "A más cristianos la *aloja* que los doctores han muerto." See: Beltrán Cortés, *Apuntes para una Historia Del Frío*, p. 198.

⁵⁵ Matías de Porrás, *Tratado sobre beber frio con nieve*, Lima: Gerónimo de Contreras, 1621.

For the conservation of the cold snow was used in important quantities. Mainly in *neveros*, constructions dedicated to preserve fresh meats, fish and drinks. The ice and snow were stored since winter in deep wells or in well insulated huts located high in the mountains.⁵⁶

An instrument that was used to preserve the drinks once cooled was a kind of thermos composed of a glass vessel, called *damajuana*, which was covered with cork and lined with *guadamecí* (wrought leather) Tarréed corks were also used to contain Basque basins of snow or ice. The most common procedure was to throw snow lumps into the beverage, others put snow over a piece of cloth, and poured water or wine, which they collected underneath...⁵⁷

The best and the healthiest method, was described by Dr. Gerónimo Pardo in his 1661 book, which instructs:

[...] but it should never be thrown directly into the drink, but instead in the vessel with the liquid to be cooled, it must be placed inside another container with snow or ice with The drink is cooled by snow, putting in the snow the carafe, canteen or other any vessel that contains it, so that it is surrounded and surrounded by snow; for whose effect one must have made a bucket, or other similar instrument, of sufficient capacity, to fit the drinking vessel and the surrounding snow [...].⁵⁸

He advises that frosty things, so that they do not harm health, should be drunk in a very narrow and narrow hole and mouth glass, such as some *garrafillas* - large

⁵⁶ For an extensive description of the use and construction of the storing facilities, commonly called *pozos de nieve* (snow wells), see: Ángel María Calvo Barco, "Los neveros, una actividad desaparecida en nuestras montañas," *Zainak, Cuaderno de Antropología y Etnografía*, No. 14, (1997), pp. 203-213; Vanessa Montesinos Muñoz, "Una aproximación a la historia de la nevera en España," *Res Mobilis*. Oviedo University Press, Vol. 2, No. 2, (2013), pp.157-167, pp. 157-158; Iván Pérez Cipriano, *Agua, máquinas y hombres en la España preindustrial*, Oviedo: Pentalfa ediciones, 2012, pp. 83-84, and María Asunción Romero Díaz, Francisco Belmonte Serrato, "Los pozos de nieve de Sierra Espuña (Murcia): aspectos históricos, culturales, geográficos y climáticos que propiciaron el desarrollo de la industria artesanal del hielo," in Concepción de la Peña Velasco (ed.), *En torno al Barroco: miradas múltiples*, Murcia: Editum, 2006, pp. 113-128.

⁵⁷ Luis De Toro, *Discursos o consideraciones sobre la materia de enfriar la bebida en que se trata de las diferencias de enfriar y del uso y propiedad de cada una: año del Señor*, Manuscript, 1569. Reprinted in Salamanca: Universidad de Salamanca, 1991, p. 255.

⁵⁸ Jeronimo Pardo, *Tratado del vino aguado y agua envinada, sobre el aforismo 56 de la sección 7 de Hipócrates*, Valladolid: en la imprenta de Valdivielso, 1661, p. 10. The book was expurgated temporarily by the Inquisition according to the Index of 1747, after freely circulating for more than 86 years.

metal or pottery vessels with a handle and spout; used to hold alcoholic beverages, *limetas* – bottles with a long neck and broad basis, and other similar instruments to drink “so that the drink is poured little by little, and does not fall much at once, nor does he drink full mouth”⁵⁹ Throughout the book, Pardo's message is that cold drinking brings about health, childbirth, and contentment, and hot drinking, ills and diseases, and sadness.

As was the case with the greatest number of novelties, the court and its surroundings were the drivers of this fashion, and especially of its trade. The supply and consumption of snow in Madrid date from the time of Carlos V and Felipe II, but it was with the court of Felipe III, already in Madrid after leaving Valladolid, when Pablo Xarquies (o Charquías), Catalan of origin, "presents in a new way of taking advantage of the industry of the ice, calling himself Inventor". He was granted the real privilege of "the ice" on August 21, 1607, and in 1608, of "the snows", being able to use common sources and public waters and make "rafts, to industry the said ice," as well as the necessary wells to conserve them, all in the Crown of Castile. They had wells in the Sierra de Madrid in the Real de Manzanares, in addition to some snowdrifts leased to the Duke of Infantado since the beginning of the XVII century. Consumption exceeded 150,000 *arrobas* daily.⁶⁰

In the Real Sitio de Aranjuez, the kings consumed the snow brought directly from the snowdrifts of the surrounding hills. Important consumption centers were Toledo, Tatana, Lorca, Murcia, and Cartagena, where the fondness for cold drinks was very large and was supplied by large wells that they had in the Espuña mountain range.⁶¹ In Valladolid we know that several wells were built on the road to Renedo, and, through the intervention of Francisco de Praves, architect and seer of the real works, we have news of what was happening with the wells of the city. Praves had a substantial role in this activity; first as owner, and later as the administrator of the wells in the service of the Crown.⁶²

⁵⁹ Pardo, *Tratado del vino aguado y agua envinada*, pp. 121-123.

⁶⁰ *Arroba* was a Portuguese and Spanish custom unit of weight, mass or volume. In weight, it was equal to 14.7 kg in Portugal and 11.5 kg in Spain.

⁶¹ Julio Valles Rojo, *La gastronomía en tiempos de Cervantes*, Madrid: Coolinary Books, 2017.

⁶² Concepción Ferrero Maeso, *Francisco de Praves (1586-1637)*, Valladolid: Junta de Castilla y León, Consejería de Educación y Cultura, 1995, pp. 65-67.

In Madrid the demand was such that large underground deposits were built at the door of the snow wells, near the current roundabout of Bilbao, to ensure the supply of the city. To keep drinks cold, there were stalls selling snow in the Villa and Corte in places as busy as Puerta del Sol. In the absence of any other means to preserve food and drinks, the sale of snow was one of the most recognized businesses all over Madrid. Snow was transported by cars pulled by animals from the Sierra de Guadarrama, traveling through the mountains and roads (if any) at night to prevent the morning sun from melting the merchandise. Bringing the snow to the villa must have been a challenge. Despite the laborious work, it was a privileged job, because, though tortuous, it was beneficial to the pocket of a few, who earned great fortunes. Such was the Catalan entrepreneur, Pedro Xarquies, who was granted the monopoly and exclusivity for the marketing of snow and ice in the Court of Madrid at the beginning of the XVIIIs.⁶³

To sell the snow in the capital, Xarquies, who although he had to pay the Crown a fifth of the amounts he earned, saw his business flourish. The cars pulled through the old Bilbao gate arrived from Peñalara with snow to be kept in large deposits before distribution to the different points of sale established in Madrid. Normally, stalls were arranged in the hallways of the noble houses of Madrid and there they were served by servants. This activity was not exclusive to the center, Xarquies also distributed ice and snow in Alcalá de Henares and in Valdemoro. The extent of demand eventually resulted in the creation of the House of Snow and Ice Arbitration of Madrid and the Kingdom, which worked until the mid-nineteenth century.⁶⁴

In the 16th century, in Spain, Pablo Xarquies appeared before Felipe III, as the inventor of a new system to extract and conserve ice. The monarch granted him a privilege of seven years to carry out this enterprise, and the House of Arbitration of the snow and ice of the Kingdom [Casa de Arbitrio de la nieve y hielos del Reino]

⁶³ Horacio Capel, "Una actividad desaparecida de las montañas mediterráneas: el comercio de la nieve,". *Revista de geografía*, [en línea], 1970, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp. 5-42.

⁶⁴ Extracted from the website of PlanVe, a Spanish tourist organization. <http://planve.es/los-refrescos-del-siglo-xviii/>, accessed 12.10.2019.

was founded, to regulate everything that had to do with ice and snow. The Crown took one-fifth of the profits, which gave its name to the appropriate tax: *el Quinto*.⁶⁵

Proof of the importance attributed to the curative properties of 'snow-water' (*agua de nieve*) is the fact that it was frequent for hospitals in Sevilla to buy several pounds of snow, mainly in summer, for 24-26 *maravedíes* per pound every few days.⁶⁶ The enemies of this cold therapy claimed that cold beverages could cause chest pain, bronchitis, stomach disturbances, and other diverse illnesses. The controversy was long-lasting, reaching even the nineteenth century, but a consensus amongst Spanish historians exists about the unique role played by Spanish medical science on this subject.⁶⁷

De la Vega y Cortezzo attributes this to José Marcelino Ortiz Barroso, with his magnificent work *Use and abuse of water* as the one who laid the foundations of modern hydrotherapy constituted as science.⁶⁸

Since ancient times it was known that adding certain salts, such as saltpeter, to water, reduces its temperature. Mentions of the uses of chemical processes in ancient texts are numerous, referred to over the centuries by many different names. In spite of these early adoptions of the chemistry, the usefulness of using saltpeter as a cooling agent did not become popular in Spain as it had in Italy, and the use of salts for cooling beverages appear in relatively few records. However, it was to a Spanish physician working in Rome, Blas Villafranca, that was attributed the first evidence of a European using saltpeter for refrigeration in 1550, noting that a saltpeter bath had become the common method of cooling wine in Rome.⁶⁹

⁶⁵ Montesinos Muñoz, "Una aproximación a la historia de la nevera en España," p. 159.

⁶⁶ The name of different Iberian accounting units between the 11th and 19th centuries.

⁶⁷ Joaquín Herrera Dávila, *El Hospital del Cardenal de Sevilla y el Doctor Hidalgo de Agüero: Visión histórico-sanitaria del Hospital de San Hermenegildo de Sevilla*, Sevilla: Fundación de cultura andaluza, 2010, pp. 156-157.

⁶⁸ Javier Lasso de la Vega y Cortezzo, *Biografía y estudio crítico de las obras del médico Nicolás Monardes*, Sevilla: Tipografía de la Revista de Tribunales, 1891, referring to José Marcelino Ortiz Barroso, *Uso y abuso del agua dulce potable interna, y externamente practicada en estado sano, y enfermo*, Sevilla: en la imprenta de las Siete Revueltas, 1736.

⁶⁹ H.E. Roscoe and C. Schorlemmer, *A Treatise on Chemistry*, London: Macmillan & Co., 1881, p. 80. Blas Villafranca, *Methodus refrigerandi ex vocato salenitro vinum, aquamque ac potus quoduis aliud genus, cui accedunt varia naturalium rerum problemata, non minus iucunda lectu, quam necessaria cognitū*, Rome: Valerio and Luigi Dorico, 1550.

4) Continuation of the debate XVIII century

The discourse of Spanish doctors of the sixteenth century about the usefulness of snow water, and about the benefits and damages that come from just drinking the water was followed in the seventeenth century by a further step, precluding the great debate that was to occupy the attention of physicians in the eighteenth century. Those works, written in the seventeenth century, sustain that doctors should give snow water on purge days.⁷⁰ Even then, cold water is considered convenient, as an aid to cathartic purgative.⁷¹ This approach is promoted in other cases as well, such as a doctor who cures burning fever with cold water in Valencia.⁷²

All these were the preliminaries of the fierce dispute that was to heat up Spanish physicians throughout the first half of the eighteenth century, so that by the last third of the same century, “So many and so numerous were the signed and anonymous writings, the invective and the insults that were crossed in the heat of the controversy, that it would be difficult for me to list them.”⁷³

⁷⁰ Burgos, *Método curativo y uso de la nieve*. Burgos was the personal physician of the marqueses de la Guardia and of the Tribunal de la Inquisición de Córdoba, 1640; Fernando Isaac Cardoso *Utilidades del agua de nieve* and Matías Porrás, *Breves advertencias para beber frío con nieve*.

⁷¹ Toribio Cote y Cobian, *Uso del agua fría en la operación de los catárticos*, Sevilla: Universidad de Sevilla, 1636,

⁷² B.A.E. (sic., anonymous), *Memorial cristiano político sobre la permanencia del Dr. D. Juan José Lopez en la ciudad de Valencia, a fin de averiguarse prácticamente su método de curar las calenturas ardientes por medio del agua fría, propinada con varias circunstancias*, Valencia: Francisco Mestre, 1684; Feliciano Gradan de Peñafiel, *Crítica médica. Respóndese al Memorial cristiano sobre la permanencia del Dr. D. Juan José Lopez en la ciudad de Valencia*, Zaragoza, 1684; Antonio Mauricio Escuer, *Hidrología Médica, que trata del uso de las aguas frías en la curación de las calenturas ardientes*, Zaragoza, 1751.

⁷³ Isidoro de la Pastora y Nieto, *Una verdad histórica relativa al uso del agua por los médicos españoles en el tratamiento de las enfermedades: Discurso que en el acto de recibir la solemne investidura de doctor en Medicina y Cirugía pronunció ante el claustro de la Universidad Central de Madrid, Facultad de Medicina*, Madrid: Imprenta de Díaz y Compañía, 1834, p. 12. As examples of this typical literature, see Vicente Pérez, *El promotor de la salud de los hombres sin dispendio el menor de sus caudales: admirable método de curar todo mal, con brevedad, seguridad, y à placer: disertación histórico-critico médico-práctica en que se establece el agua por remedio universal de las dolencias*, Toledo: Francisco Martin, 1752. A contemporary article researches this debate: Pilar León Sanz y Dolores Baretino Coloma, “La Polémica Del Agua,” in *Vicente Ferrer Gorraiz Beaumont y Montesa (1718-1792), un polemista navarro de la Ilustración, Volumen 6 of Temas de la Historia de la Medicina*, Navarra: Gobierno de Navarra, Departamento de Salud, 2007, pp.91-150, pp. 110-111.

A fundamental characteristic of eighteenth-century therapy, along the Hippocratic thinking. We can appreciate in the Enlightenment a rebirth of a blind faith in the *vix medicatrix naturae* (literally "the healing power of nature"). Thus, Hippocratic texts are translated and discussed – enlightened clinicians tend to respect the healing action of the human organism and conclude that the role of the practical physician is to help nature in its use and act according to its dictates. The consequences are the return to natural resources (use of diets, hydrotherapy, etc.), the simplification of the compositions of some medications, the reduction in the number of remedies applied to the same patient, and the appearance of physical therapies.

5) Conclusions

The controversy around cold water did not end the habit of drinking cooled drinks, let alone in areas where the heat was unbearable in summer, for example, in Seville.

Progress always has advocates and detractors, hence we witness arduous controversies about drinking cold, though it was generally considered an improvement in the quality of life in certain latitudes of Southern Europe, and especially Spain. It became also a lucrative business, a fashion, and a custom that came to stay definitively in everyday life. Proof of its extent is that the controversy over cold drinking develops in vernacular fiction, far from Latin, the language reserved for science, with vulgar texts seeking a wider audience, not necessarily initiated in medical matters. This literary fiction contributed to wide dissemination of doctrine and therefore to greater influence on public opinion, with few exceptions, the publishers in Spanish romance were clearly in favor of the consumption of cold water and the use of snow.

However, it is more than likely, as we have seen, that many excesses were committed out of snobbism in this area, and that, like all innovations, it should be looked at with suspicion for different reasons: moral, health, and also religious. Considering it a vice, most conservative and cautious doctors warned of the risks of cold drinks, believing it to be the cause and trigger of the collapse of young

healthy people, who lead a licentious life. But even the fear of sudden death caused by a cold beverage, told in various accounts, did not even really influence the custom, whether they were cases of fatalities among anonymous, fictional, or rich and famous patients.

The divergence of positions in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries can be summarized as follows: the most reluctant theories of Andrés Laguna and Cristóbal de Vega, noted in some chapters of their texts, which influenced the unedited work of Luis de Toro, gave way to others more permissive authors of composite monographs, who were clearly in favor of cooling water and drinks in general. The first was Francisco Franco, to which texts of Nicolás Monardes, Francisco Micó and Alonso Díez Daza were later added. However, a common doctrine can be detected, the result of the Hippocratic Galenism prevailing in Renaissance medicine. Thus, not committing excesses in the diet that potentially included the danger of excessive cooling, which for some must be avoided at all costs, while for others it can be graduated without further consequences.

Quoting from a study of the works of the doctor Nicolás Monardes – an awarded memory by Javier Lasso de la Vega y Cortezzo:

...Spain deserves the glory of being the first nation that has made clear the benefits of water in its various states and its surgical and medical uses.... Seville has been the cradle of the illustrious men who have carried out this work...⁷⁴

⁷⁴ De la Vega y Cortezzo, *Biografía y estudio crítico de las obras*, p. 38.